

28 displayed against various contextual data, but the 3D geometry itself loses its detail
29 and quality. The paper discusses the limitations of the procedure and future research
30 directions.

31 **Keywords:** BIM; GIS; FME; 3D visualization; georeferencing

32 1. Introduction

33 BIM (*Building Information Modeling*) is defined as a digital representation of the
34 physical and functional characteristics of any building object that provides a reliable
35 basis for decision-making throughout its life cycle [1]. It is also the process by which
36 information about a building or group of buildings is generated and managed [2]. A
37 BIM model contains highly detailed and semantically rich information about a
38 structure [3]. Building information modeling has become one of the latest trends in the
39 construction industry, which is constantly evolving [4]. BIM has quickly become the
40 primary approach to digitally integrating data and information about the design,
41 implementation and management of building structures [5]. It has allowed
42 stakeholders to capture and share information in an efficient and productive manner
43 [6]. BIM is being used to bridge the interoperability gap between different industries,
44 increasing its popularity among clients and designers [7]. BIM is now considered to
45 facilitate integration, interoperability, collaboration and process automation in the
46 construction industry [8]. The implementation of BIM in Poland is progressing [9], and
47 BIM models in modern architecture and building management are an essential
48 prerequisite for the successful emergence of construction projects. Thanks to the
49 semantic richness of the data (geometric and non-graphic), BIM applies in the design
50 of new buildings, in the retrofitting of existing buildings [10], ensuring safety on site
51 [11] or the efficient implementation of projects [12]. Highly detailed geometric data is
52 generated during BIM processes and can be integrated with GIS (*Geographical*
53 *Information System*) data structures. However, the compatibility of the two worlds is
54 fraught with many questions and problems [13].

55 There are many benefits to integrating geospatial data into the design process [14]. A
56 GIS represents various aspects of the real world in a digital environment, ranging from
57 a variety of geodetic information in different coordinate systems to infinite datasets
58 updated in real time. GIS technologies have evolved significantly over the past decade
59 [15]. A GIS can be defined as a system designed to store, retrieve, manage, display and
60 analyze all types of geographic and spatial data. GIS information combines with
61 attributes of geographic locations to show what is properly located in a specific area
62 [16]. GIS technology is used in many different fields. For example, in the construction
63 industry, GIS is used in the construction planning process or reviewing the project
64 schedule for gravity dams, where topography plays an important role. Without the
65 geospatial data provided by GIS, the implementation of such a project would be
66 impossible [17]. GIS also enables planners and designers to quickly and efficiently
67 create and test alternative development scenarios for a given site. It also determines
68 their likely impact on the future environment, e.g., land use analyses and related
69 population and employment trends, enabling informed planning decisions [18].

70 The topic of BIM and GIS integration has been an area of research for many years,
71 especially at the level of combining data from these systems [19]. In some studies,
72 commercial tools such as FME (*Feature Manipulation Engine*) developed by Safe
73 Software are used for data conversion, management and visualization. Such a tool is
74 capable of handling data conversion tasks, such as geometry assignment and
75 georeferencing or data semantics [20]. For example, the software given above was used
76 in a study aimed at visualizing a 3D model made in IFC (*Industry Foundation Classes*)
77 format of the Church of Santa Maria dei Miracoli in Venice in a GIS environment, in
78 order to digitize 3D documentation of historical cultural heritage [21]. Another
79 example of application was a study done on integrated modeling between CityGML
80 (*City Geography Markup Language*) and IFC formats for the analysis of urban
81 microclimates for urban development and neighborhoods. FME was then used to
82 convert data from IFC format to CityGML format [22]. However, there is a lack of

83 applications for existing buildings that could be digitized into a digital model, which
84 in turn could feed GIS spatial reference databases (in Poland, for example, the Land
85 and Building Register). The correct location of the BIM model in GIS space also enables
86 reliable analyses and simulations (e.g., insolation) [23].

87 Hence, the purpose of this work was to attempt to give proper georeferencing to an
88 existing BIM model of a historic site in a GIS environment, and then convert the data
89 to Shapefile format (which can feed reference databases), using FME software.

90 2. Methodology

91 The BIM model used was a building located on Constitution Square in Warsaw,
92 Poland. The model was obtained from an internal repository of BIM models
93 maintained by Warsaw University of Technology. A topographic map from the ESRI
94 geoportal and 3D building geospatial layers with the CityGML LOD2 level of detail
95 (Fig. 1) in Shapefile (.shp) format were used as reference data. The data were placed in
96 the 1992 coordinate system.

97

98 Figure 1: The building model used. Source: own elaboration based on the model
99 obtained from the repository of BIM models maintained by the Warsaw University of
100 Technology.

101 Tools from three software vendors were used to achieve the goal: Safe Software (FME),
102 Autodesk (Autodesk Revit), and ESRI (ArcGIS Pro). The BIM model made in Autodesk

103 Revit was uploaded to FME software, which allows the appropriate coordinate system
104 to be assigned and the file to be converted to Shapefile (.shp) form. ArcGIS Pro was
105 used to locate the BIM model (.rvt) in GIS space and later present the data after
106 assigning the appropriate georeferencing (Fig. 2).

108 Figure 2: Flow chart of the procedure process. Source: own development.

109 In order to integrate the BIM data into the GIS environment, first the assignment of a
110 suitable base point and the change of the unit of work to meters was performed in
111 Revit software. Next, the X and Y coordinates of the points for which the assigned base
112 point would be located in the GIS environment were checked in ArcGIS Pro (Fig. 3).

114 Figure 3: Setting the base point to a known base point and checking the X and Y
115 coordinates. Source: own development.

116 The next step was visual programming in FME software (Fig. 4). After uploading the
117 Revit file to FME, 3 tools were used to give the BIM model the proper georeferencing
118 and coordinates:

- 119 • "Offsetter" - used to set the reference point to 0,0 coordinates,
- 120 • "3DRotator" - used to rotate the object towards true north if required,
- 121 • "LocalCoordinateSystem" - used to give the appropriate coordinate system and
122 coordinates of our building (base point).

123 In addition, 3 more tools were used to retain information about the features of the
124 model:

- 125 • "AttributeManager" - used to export attribute information from the BIM model
126 to a new attribute table in the Shapefile,
- 127 • "AttributeExposer" - used for possible modification, copying or renaming of
128 attributes,
- 129 • "AttributeRemover" - used to select the data to be visualized in the output file.

130 In the last step, the file was exported to Shapefile (.shp) format using the
131 "FeatureWriter" tool. Such an exported file was already ready to be displayed in
132 ArcGIS Pro.

133

134 Figure 4: Diagram of model construction in FME software. Source: own development.

135 3. Results

136 Transformation processes performed in FME, it was possible to display the processed
137 building model into shapefile format in ArcGIS Pro. The corresponding tools enabled
138 correct georeferencing and appropriate geographic coordinates in the specified
139 coordinate system (Fig. 5). Thus, the building outline agrees with the actual state
140 within the required margin of error that the land and building registry assumes (up to
141 10 cm). On this basis, the boundaries of the building property can be plotted into
142 reference databases.

143
144 Figure 5: The building model in 2D view after georeferencing and coordinates (left)
145 and the location of the building against a topographic map from ESRI (right) in ArcGIS
146 Pro. Source: own development.

147 The imported model in shapefile format adopts "multipatch" geometry and can be
148 displayed in two-dimensional and three-dimensional views (Fig. 6). Thanks to the

149 integration of the building model with the ArcGIS Pro environment, all available
150 functions in this program can be used in conjunction with BIM data.

151

152

153 Figure 6: Building model in 3D view in ArcGIS Pro. Source: own development.

154

155 Figure 7: Building model in 3D view against the background of buildings with
156 CityGML LOD2 level of detail. Source: own development.

157 The building in ArcGIS Pro, compared to the model in Revit, retained a relatively good
158 level of detail (Fig. 7). When zoomed in, detailed elements such as stairs, balconies and
159 windows, among others, are visible in the Shapefile model (Figures 8 and 9).

160

161 Figure 8: Balcony with windows in ArcGIS Pro (left) and Revit (right) software.

162 Source: own development.

163

164 Figure 9: Comparison of 3D models in ArcGIS Pro (top) and Revit (bottom) software.

165 Source: own development.

166 Exporting data from a BIM model to a table in a Shapefile also makes it possible in
167 ArcGIS Pro software to select elements based on data in an attribute table. For example,
168 it is possible to color-code a building based on Revit families or display families of
169 interest (Figure 10).

170

171 Figure 10: Color breakdown of the building model based on Revit families. Source:
 172 own development.

173 However, the building model in Shapefile format does not reflect the BIM model 100
 174 percent. In some places, "holes" in the model can be seen, probably resulting from
 175 errors in data transformation or in the FME software's reading of the data. This error
 176 is hardly noticeable and only noticeable at close approximation (Fig. 11). The color of
 177 materials or visibility of building materials used in Revit is also lost.

178

179 Figure 11: Example of a "hole" in the model in ArcGIS Pro software. Source: own
180 development.

181 **4. Conclusion**

182 The presented method of integrating BIM data into a GIS environment showed that it
183 is possible to interact between two theoretically dichotomous formats, avoiding data
184 loss regardless of their typology. The steps presented in the paper ensure the correct
185 georeferencing of BIM models in GIS. The FME software used contains the key
186 functionalities necessary for this topic in assigning the appropriate coordinate system
187 and converting data from Revit file (.rvt) format to Shapefile (.shp) format. The
188 progressive integration of BIM and GIS systems increases the spectrum of challenges
189 facing practitioners and researchers. The work presented here is one of several
190 examples of the implementation of such a topic and also one of the less expensive
191 solutions. The future application of one or another BIM AND GIS data flow is already
192 dependent on the organizational and financial issues of the company. Nevertheless, a
193 realistic three-dimensional view of models in an appropriately localized area enables

194 better preparation of analyses and simulations or problem solving for future
195 investments.

196 **References**

- 197 1. Zhao, X.: A scientometric review of global BIM research: Analysis and
198 visualization, *Automation in Construction*, Volume 80, Pages 37-47, ISSN 0926-
199 5805 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2017.04.002>, 2017 [Accessed on 18.01.2024]
200
- 201 2. Peckienė, A, Ustinovičius L.: Possibilities for Building Spatial Planning using
202 BIM Methodology, *Procedia Engineering*, Volume 172, Pages 851-858, ISSN
203 1877-7058, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2017.02.085>, 2017 [Accessed on
204 18.01.2024]
205
- 206 3. Rafiee, A., Dias, E. , Fruijtjer, S., Scholten, H.: From BIM to Geo-analysis: View
207 Coverage and Shadow Analysis by BIM/GIS Integration, *Procedia
208 Environmental Sciences*, Volume 22, Pages 397-402, ISSN 1878-0296,
209 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proenv.2014.11.037>, 2014 [Accessed on 18.01.2024]
210
- 211 4. Borkowski, A. S. (2023). Evolution of BIM: epistemology, genesis and division
212 into periods. *Journal of Information Technology in Construction (ITcon)*, 28(34),
213 646-661.
214
- 215 5. Borkowski, A. S., Kochański, Ł., Wyszomirski, M.: Case Study on Building
216 Information (BIM) and Land Information (LIM) Models Including Geospatial
217 Data. *Geomatics and Environmental Engineering*. 17. Pages 19-34
218 <https://doi.org/10.7494/geom.2023.17.1.19>, 2022 [Accessed on 18.01.2024]
219
- 220 6. Tiveron, A. (2020). „e-BIM. The methodology of information modeling in a
221 “result” economy, *Selfpublishing with Amazon*, (s 392).
222
- 223 7. Shirowzhan, S., Sepasgozar, S. M., Edwards, D. J., Li, H., & Wang, C. (2020).
224 BIM compatibility and its differentiation with interoperability challenges as an
225 innovation factor. *Automation in Construction*, 112, 103086.
226
- 227 8. Fosu, R., Suprabhas, K., Rathore, Z., Cory, C.: Integration of Building
228 Information Modeling (BIM) and Geographic Information Systems (GIS)—a
229 literature review and future needs. *Proceedings of the 32nd CIB W78
230 Conference, Eindhoven, The Netherlands, Pages 27-29,*
231 <https://itc.scix.net/pdfs/w78-2015-paper-020.pdf>, 2015 [Accessed on 18.01.2024]
232

- 233 9. Mitera-Kielbasa, E. & Zima, K. (2023). BIM Policy in Eastern Europe. *Civil and*
234 *Environmental Engineering Reports*, 33(4), 14-22.
235
- 236 10. Radzik, Ł., & Schabowicz, K. (2015). Wykorzystanie BIM w remontach
237 obiektów budowlanych. *Materiały budowlane*, (11), 144-146. (in Polish)
238
- 239 11. Drozd, W., & Kowalik, M. (2016). Wykorzystanie BIM do zapewnienia
240 bezpieczeństwa pracy na budowie. *Materiały budowlane*, (6), 50-51. (in Polish)
241
- 242 12. Szóstak, M. (2023). Forecasting the Course of Cumulative Cost Curves for
243 Different Construction Projects. *Civil and Environmental Engineering Reports*,
244 33(1), 71-89.
245
- 246 13. Günther-Diringer, D.: From BIM to GIS at the Smithsonian Institution, *Proc. Int.*
247 *Cartogr. Assoc.*, 1, 52, <https://doi.org/10.5194/ica-proc-1-52-2018>, 2018
248 [Accessed on 10.01.2024]
249
- 250 14. Guyo, E., Hartmann, T., & Ungureanu, L. (2021). Interoperability between BIM
251 and GIS through open data standards: An overview of current literature. *sign*,
252 3, 5-9.
253
- 254 15. Shkundalov, D., Vilutienė, T.: Bibliometric analysis of Building Information
255 Modeling, Geographic Information Systems and Web environment integration,
256 *Automation in Construction*, Volume 128, ISSN 0926-5805,
257 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2021.103757>, 2021 [Accessed on 18.01.2024]
258
- 259 16. Weerasinghe, M. D. G., Rupasinghe A. R., Jayasooriya S. D.: *Application of GIS*
260 *in construction management*, 2018
261
- 262 17. Basir, W. A., Majid, W. N. F., Ujang, U., Chong, A.: Integration of GIS and BIM
263 techniques in construction project management – a review, *Int. Arch.*
264 *Photogramm. Remote Sens. Spatial Inf. Sci.*, XLII-4/W9, 307–316,
265 <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLII-4-W9-307-2018>, 2018 [Accessed on
266 21.01.2024]
267
- 268 18. Sultani, R., Soliman, A., Al-Hagla, K.: The use of geographic information system
269 (GIS) based spatial decision support system (SDSS) in developing the urban
270 planning process. *Architecture & planning journal*, 1, Pages 97-115,
271 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/273457666_The_Use_of_Geographic

- 272 _Information_System_GIS_Based_Spatial_Decision_Support_System_SDSS_in
273 _Developing_the_Urban_Planning_Process, 2009 [Accessed on 18.01.2024]
274
- 275 19. Sani, M. J., & Abdul Rahman, A. (2018). GIS and BIM integration at data level:
276 A review. *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing*
277 and *Spatial Information Sciences*, 42, 299-306.
278
- 279 20. Zhu, J., Wu, P.: BIM/GIS data integration from the perspective of information
280 flow. *Automation in Construction* Volume 136: ARTN 104166,
281 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2022.104166>, 2022 [Accessed on 10.01.2024]
282
- 283 21. Matrone, F., Colucci, E., De Ruvo, V., Lingua, A., and Spanò, A.: HBIM in a
284 semantic 3D GIS database, *Int. Arch. Photogramm. Remote Sens. Spatial Inf. Sci.*
285 XLII-2/W11, 857–865, [https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLII-2-W11-857-](https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLII-2-W11-857-2019)
286 2019, 2019 [Accessed on 10.01.2024]
287
- 288 22. Jusuf, S. K., Mosseau, B., Godfroid G., Soh V. J. H.: Integrated modeling of
289 CityGML and IFC for city/neighborhood development for urban microclimates
290 analysis *Energy Procedia*, Volume 122, Pages 145-150, ISSN 1876-6102,
291 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2017.07.329>, 2017 [Accessed on 10.01.2024]
292
- 293 23. Borkowski, A. S.: Ekologia narzędzi BIM – georeferencja modeli obiektów
294 budowlanych z wykorzystaniem CDE, *Przegląd Budowlany*, 12, 2023, 158-162.
295 (in Polish)
296